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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Cream for Wound Healing Activity

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ABSTRACT

With the development of medical science, wound care is continually changing. Professionals in wound care are still searching for the ideal dressing material since they are up against a number of obstacles. In order to control wounds, wound care experts have turned back to the old healing techniques by adopting traditional and alternative medicine due to the advent of multi-resistant organisms and a decline in modern antibiotics. The prepared formulations are then evaluated for parameters like physical properties, pH, viscosity, Spreadability and stability of the formulated cream. The prepared formulations showed good Spreadability, no evidence of phase separation and good consistency during the study period. Stability parameters like visual appearance, nature, viscosity and pH of the formulations showed that there was no significant variation during the study period. The prepared formulations showed proper pH range that is approximately pH 6; it confirms the compatibility of the formulations with skin secretions.

INTRODUCTION

Creams are the semisolid dosage forms and intended. For topical application to the skin, placed on the surface of eye, or used nasally, vaginally or rectally for therapeutic or protective action or cosmetic function. These preparations are used for the localized effects produced at the site of their application by drug penetration in to

the underlying layer of skin or mucous membrane. These products are designed to deliver drug into the skin in treating dermal disorders, with the skin as the target organ. Creams are semi-solid emulsions of oil and water. They are divided into two types: oil-in-water (O/W) creams which are composed of small droplets of oil dispersed in a continuous phase, and water-in-oil (W/O) creams which are composed of small droplets of water

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dispersed in a continuous oily phase, Oil in-water creams are more comfortable and cosmetically acceptable as they are less greasy and more easily washed off using water. Water-in-oil creams are more difficult to handle but many drugs which are incorporated into creams are hydrophobic and will be released more readily from a water-in-oil cream than an oil-in-water cream. Water-in-oil creams are also more moisturising as they provide an oily barrier which reduces water loss from the stratum corneum, the outermost layer of the skin, World Health Organization (WHO) as well our country has been promoting traditional medicine because they are less expensive, easily available and comprehensive, especially in developing countries. It is also true that eight percent of the world's population relies on medicinal plants for their primary health care. Whole world including the developed country recognized the importance of traditional medicine and has treatment strategies, guidelines and standard for ethno medicine, Creams are semisolid dosage forms that are meant to be applied topically to the skin, on the eye's surface, or utilised nasally, vaginally, or rectally for medicinal or protective action. They can also serve an aesthetic purpose. These preparations are utilised for the localised effects that the drug's penetration into the skin's or mucous membrane's underlying layer produces at the application location. The skin is the intended organ for these devices medication delivery systems, which are intended to treat cutaneous ailments. Wound may be defined as a loss or breaking of cellular and anatomic or functional continuity of living tissue. It is produced by physical, chemical, thermal, microbial, or immunological damage to the tissue. Wound healing or wound repair is the body's natural process of regenerating dermal and epidermal tissue.

3.0 Aim and objective :-

Aim :-To prepare new formulation by taking herbal drug using there biological activity like antiseptic, wound healing activity, antioxidant, cell repairing etc.

Objective:-

- To prevent further tissue damage.
- To promote healing.
- To absorb inflammatory exudate and to promote drainages.
- To convert the contaminated wound into a clean wound.
- To prevent hemorrhage.
- To apply medication in place.
- To restore the function of the part.
- To provide physical and mental comfort to the patient.
- To provide maintenance of high humidity between the wound and dressings
- Reduce pain and fastly treat wound

4.0 Plan of work:-

- 1) Collection of herbal drug
- 2) Selection of chemical or excipients
- 3) Prepare formulation
- 4) Chemical or laboratory testing herbal drug
- 5) Formulation testing
- 6) Apparatus and instrument :
- 7) Beaker, stirred, measuring cylinder, waterbath, glass rod, mortar and pastel ,thermometer, pH paper,

5.0 MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Sr.no	Ingredient	Formulation	Role of ingredient
1.	Turmeric powder	2.7 mg	Antiseptics & Anti-inflammatory
2.	Aloe Vera gel	2.8 ml	Anti-aging,cooling effect
3.	Tulsi powder	1.7 mg	Antibacterial
4.	Arjuna bark powder	0.9 mg	Wounds healing
5.	Bees wax	5.45 mg	Emulsifying agent
6.	Liquid paraffin	18.1 ml	Lubricating agent
7.	Borax	0.36 mg	Alkaline agent
8.	Methyl Paraben	0.03 mg	Preservative
9.	Distilled water	q. s.	Vehicle
10.	Rose Water	q. s.	Fragrance

1)Aloe vera :-

Aloe is the dried juice of the leaves of Aloe barbadensis Miller [curacao aloe],Aloe perryi baker [socotrine aloe],hybrids of Aloe ferox Miller and aloe africana Miller or aloe spicata baker [cope alpes] Family :- Liliaceae

A significant medicinal plant for treating and defending the skin is aloe vera. It is incredibly beneficial and protective and works wonders on burns, sunburns, and a range of skin conditions (eczema, psoriasis, acne). Aloe Vera aids in the restoration of even the most delicate skin injuries. Aloe gel, however, may actually slow the healing process in some cases of severe burns.

Benefits of aloe-vera

- It has a cooling impact on rashes or sunburns.
- Its anti-inflammatory effects can lessen pain, swelling, and soreness of wounds or injuries.
- Hydrate the skin with essential .
- Prevents premature ageing.
- Prevent or decrease wrinkles and dark spots on your face.^[4]

Chemical constituents:-

○ Barbaloin [C- glycoside]

○ Resin

○ Aloe -emodin

○ Isobarbalion

Aloinosides A&B

Fig No.14 :- Aloe Vera

2) Arjuna bark:-

The Arjun Tree, also known as **Terminalia Arjuna**, is well known in Ayurveda for a multitude of health and skincare benefits. The bark of this tree is the main medicinal component used for therapeutic purposes. Along with Arjuna powder benefits in numerous skin issue, it is also known for its cardioprotective actions. The

medicinal properties of *T. Arjuna* range from antioxidant, hypotensive, anti-atherogenic, anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic, and anti-mutagenic to gastro-productive effects.

Arjuna consists of dried stem bark of the plant known as Terminalia Arjuna Rob

Family:- Combretaceae

Chemical constituents:-

- 15% of tannins [hydrolysable & condensed]
- Triterpenoidsaponins
Arjunoicacid, Arjunicacid, Arjungenin

Ellagic acid

Fig No.19:- Heating Process

Fig No.20:- Trituration Process

Fig No.15:- Arjun Bark

1] Bees wax :

Beeswax has historical uses. Using high-temperature gas chromatography and mass spectrometry patterns in extracts of ancient pottery, it has been determined that beeswax was harvested and used by Neolithic peoples (Roffet-Salque et al., 2015). Beeswax is a complex chemical mixture secreted by the abdominal wax glands of honeybees (Fratini et al., 2016; Bogdanov, 2016). Bees, between 12–18 days of age (postemergence), secrete beeswax as a liquid which hardens on contact with air. Beeswax is used to make the foundation and honeycomb hexagonal cells used for raising the brood and storage of honey and pollen (Bogdanov, 2016).

2] Liquid paraffin :

Liquid paraffin is a mixture of liquid hydrocarbons. Its main use has been as a lubricant laxative but it is not recommended, because of its adverse effects. Nevertheless, it continues to be used for this purpose and is reportedly as effective as lactulose

Fig No.21:- Final Formulation

6.0 Evolution test:

Phytochemical test of herbal drugs

A) Aloe identification test:-

1. prepare 1% solution of Aloe by boiling with water, add 0.5% of kielguhr to it following test:- a) Heat 5 ml of above test solution with 0.2 g of borax, add this solution to the test tube containing water. A green fluorescence is produced [due to aloemodin]

B) Arjuna identification test:-

Tannins:- 0.5 g of the extract was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water, then a few drops of 1% ferric chloride solution was added to obtain a brownish green or blue black precipitate, which confirms the presence of tannin.

❖ Evaluation of Herbal Cream :-

1) pH:

The pH meter was calibrated and measured the pH by placing in the beaker containing 20mg of the cream. base was found to be in range of 6.2-6.9

which is good for skin pH. All the formulations of cream base were shown pH nearer to skin required.

2) Determination of homogeneity:

The formulations were tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch.

3) Accelerated stability testing

Accelerated stability testing of prepared formulations was conducted for 2 most stable formulations at room temperature, studied for 7 days. They were formulation number 4 and 5 at $40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 days. The formulations were kept both at room and elevated temperature and observed on 0th, 5th, 10th, 15th and 20th day for the following parameters.

4) Dye test:

The test was done by mixing the cream with red dye then place the drop of cream. was placed on a slide and covered with cover slip, observed under microscope. If the dispersion phase appears in red colored globules the cream was O/W type. If the continuous phase appears red color the cream was w/o type.

5) Homogeneity:

The test was done by physical touch with hands.

6) Appearance:

The appearance of the cream was found by observing its color, opacity, etc.

7) Smear type:

The test was conducted after the application of cream on the skin the smear formed was oily or aqueous in nature.

8) Determination of emolliency :

Emolliency, slipperiness and amount application of fixed amounts of cream was checked.

9)Determination of viscosity:

The viscosity determinations were carried out using a Brookfield Viscometer using spindle number S-64 at a 20 rpm at a temperature of 25°C. The determinations were carried out in triplicate and the average of three readings was recorded.

10)Washability:

The removal of the cream applied on skin was done by washing under tap water with minimal force to remove the cream.

11)Irritancy test:

The cream was applied on left hand dorsal side surface of Isq.cm and observed. in equal intervals up to 24hrs for irritancy, redness and edema.

7.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In first consultation patient had severe pain, mild swelling, serous discharge and large wound at medial malleolus. As wound was big and multiple sufficient amount of prepared *Arjuna* bark powder was applied on all wounds and bandaged.

Sr.no	Test parameter	Result
1	Colour	Yellowish brown
2	Odour	Characteristics
3	Consistency	Semi solid
4	Texture	Smooth
5	pH	5-6
6	Washability	Easy to wash
7	Irritancy test	No Irritating

8.0 CONCLUSION

Formulation of Herbal Skin Cream for wound healing was successfully developed that met the relevant pharmaceutical characteristics. The prepared formulations showed good physico chemical characteristics and the pH is compatible with the skin secretions and release was the best for formulation . The creams were found to be stable during stability study conducted for 3 months. From the present study it can be concluded that it is possible to develop creams containing herbal extracts and can be used as the provision of a barrier to protect skin. Plants are more potent healers because they promote the repair mechanism in the natural way. The wound healing property of the formulated herbal skin cream has yet to be experimented and will be done in future The prepared cream was pleasant,

coolant, easily spreadable and washable thereby there is a chance of increased the patient compliance. Formulated cream significantly promotes wound healing than control or non-medicated group. This study can be helpful for upcoming researchers to select these herbs for the formulation and evaluation of other cosmetic applications which can be claimed for their efficacy with scientific data

Expected outcome of proposed work :-

Decrease bacterial concentration within the wound bed and the risk of infection. Increase the effectiveness of topical antimicrobials. Improve the bactericidal activity of leukocytes. Shorten the inflammatory phase of wound healing. Decrease the energy required by the body for wound

healing. Eliminate the physical barrier to wound healing.

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